

Gauteng urban area surveys 2. Checklist of the spiders of the Groenkloof Nature Reserve in Pretoria, South Africa (Arachnida, Araneae)

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ABSTRACT: Little is known about the diversity of spiders in urban areas in South Africa. This survey of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) forms part of the Spider Monitoring in Cities (SMC) project of SANSa. The results of sampling undertaken in the Groenkloof Nature Reserve in the Gauteng province, South Africa, are provided. A total of 112 species, 84 genera, from 35 families were recorded. Sampling was mainly done by sweeping and hand collecting. The most species-rich families were the Salticidae (20 spp.), Gnaphosidae (12 spp.), followed by the Lycosidae (11 spp.), while 16 families are represented by singletons. The conservation status and level of endemism based on their known distribution are provided for each species. Two of the species are Vulnerable and two are Endangered.

Keywords: conservation, endemism, diversity, South African National Survey of Arachnida, urban surveys

INTRODUCTION

It is estimated that 16.8% of the South African human population resides in Gauteng, and the province has the highest population density and the highest urbanisation levels. Consequently, the biodiversity in the province is highly threatened by industrialisation, mining, agriculture, and especially urbanisation. There are current high demands for the provision of land and basic services to alleviate poor living conditions. Therefore, the successful conservation of biodiversity within Gauteng requires the identification of priority areas where development and habitat transformation should be discouraged, and conservation efforts should be put in place.

Interest in the invertebrate faunas of urban and suburban areas has increased in the last 20 years. These areas are not just seen as human-modified habitats of low intrinsic biodiversity, but as potential corridors for dispersal of wildlife through urban areas, both within and outside towns and cities. As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), few papers on spider diversity in urban and suburban areas have been published in the last few years (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). In the Free State, several studies have been undertaken in the Free State National Botanical Garden, Bloemfontein (Butler & Haddad, 2011; Haddad *et al.*, 2019; Neethling & Haddad, 2013), while in the Eastern Cape a checklist of the spiders of Jeffreys Bay was provided (Wiese & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2023). In Gauteng, surveys were undertaken in several reserves in Pretoria (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Lyle, 2014) as part of the Spider Monitoring in Cities (SMC) project of SANSa. The first paper dealt with the diversity of the Faerie Glenn Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Webb, 2022).

Groenkloof Nature Reserve was the first game sanctuary in Africa proclaimed by President Paul Kruger in 1895. Its main purpose was to protect the Oribi and other game that were being wiped out by hunters. After 1910, part of the area was rented out for the establishment of commercial plantations for the delivery of wood and the production of paper. By the late 1950s, the City Council of Pretoria became the owner of the area. When the reserve was proclaimed in 1994, the plantations were removed to allow the natural vegetation to regenerate and since 1999 the reserve was stocked with various game species.

This paper presents the first species list on the spider fauna of the Groenkloof Nature Reserve. Information on endemism and conservation status for each of the 112 species is provided.

Figures 1–3. In the Groenkloof Nature Reserve the highveld and bushveld regions meet on low, broken ridges varying in steepness. Photos: 2 & 3. Peter Webb.

Fig. 4. Survey area Groenkloof Nature Reserve, Gauteng.

METHOD

Study area: Groenkloof Nature Reserve (25°47'S, 28°12'E) (GNR) is located adjacent to the Fountains Valley at the southern entrance to Pretoria. The reserve of 600 ha is managed by the Department of Nature Conservation. GNR is only 5 km from the Pretoria city centre and borders the Fountains Valley in its northern part.

Vegetation: GNR is situated where the highveld and bushveld regions meet and features low, broken ridges varying in steepness. Open grassland occurs along the Apies Valley and the higher plateau. The vegetation is semipen thicket, dominated by a variety of woody species, including *Senegalia caffra*, *Searsia leptodictya*, *Combretum mole*, and *Dombeya rotundifolia*. The under-story is dominated by a variety of grasses. A mature woodland of white stinkwood trees is also present on the reserve.

Sampling methods and identification: The second author (RL) and third author (PW) sampled spiders over a period of 10 years. Live spiders were sampled, photographed, and then preserved in 70% ethanol by PW. Identifications were done in Pretoria by the first author (ASD). Voucher specimens are housed in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the ARC Plant Health and Protection division in Pretoria. Some of the species could not be identified to species level because they were immature or the taxonomy of some families is still unresolved.

Endemicity value: The endemicity value for each species is provided (Table 3) based on its currently known distribution. Seven endemicity categories are recognised: 6 = when GNR is the type locality; 5 = GE, endemic to the Gauteng province but wider than the type locality; 4 = SAE endemic to South Africa but known from two adjoining provinces; 3 = SAE South African endemic, known from more than two provinces or two provinces not adjoining; 2 = STHE, endemic to Southern Africa (south of Zambezi and Kunene Rivers); 1 = AE, known from the Afrotropical Region (African Endemic); 0 = cosmopolitan, Africa and wider (C).

Conservation status: As part of the Red Listing Spider Project (Foord *et al.*, 2020), the preliminary conservation status of all South African species is now available. Immatures, new species, and undetermined taxa were not evaluated (NE). Species known from only one sex, or where only very old material is available, or species that could not be identified were listed as DD (Data Deficient). Species with a broad distribution (categories 0–2) were considered to be of least concern (LC); those of categories 3 and 4 were considered to be South African endemics (SAE) and many of them are also LC; while species of special concern usually belong to categories 5 or 6.

TABLE 1: Spider diversity of Groenkloof Nature Reserve with the total number of families, genera (GEN) and species (SPP.).

FAMILY	GEN	SPP.	FAMILY	GEN	SPP.
Agelenidae	1	1	Palpimanidae	1	1
Amaurobiidae	1	1	Philodromidae	2	2
Ammoxenidae	1	1	Pholcidae	1	1
Araneidae	4	4	Phyxelididae	1	1
Atypidae	1	1	Pisauridae	3	3
Bemmeridae	1	1	Prodidomidae	2	2
Caponiidae	1	1	Salticidae	10	20
Cheiracanthiidae	2	2	Scytodidae	1	2
Clubionidae	1	1	Sparassidae	1	1
Corinnidae	1	1	Sicariidae	1	2
Cyrtacheniidae	1	1	Stasimopidae	1	1
Dictynidae	1	1	Theraphosidae	2	2
Eresidae	2	2	Theridiidae	4	4
Gnaphosidae	9	12	Thomisidae	6	8
Idiopidae	4	6	Trachelidae	1	1
Linyphiidae	2	2	Uloboridae	2	2
Lycosidae	6	11	Zodariidae	4	4
Oxyopidae	2	6		84	112

TABLE 2: Conservation status and endemicity of the spider species sampled at the Groenkloof Nature Reserve.

CONSERVATION STATUS	CODE	NO SPP.	%
Data deficient	DD	3	2.8
Not evaluated	NE	3	2.8
Least concern	LC	103	91.8
Vulnerable	V	2	1.8
Endangered	EN	2	1.8
ENDEMICITY			
0 – Africa and wider (C)	LC	8	7.1
1 – African endemics (AE)	LC	42	37.5
2 – Southern African endemics (STHE)	LC	29	25.9
3 – SA endemics (SAE):	LC	25	22.3
4 – SA (SAE): 2 adjacent provinces		3	2.8
5 – Gauteng endemics (GE)		3	2.7
6 – Type locality		0	

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Numbers present: A total of 112 species, 84 genera, from 35 families were recorded (Tables 1 & 3). Two species of the Oxyopidae and Zodariidae could not be identified to species level as their taxonomy was still unresolved. As part of the SMC project of SANSa, the first survey dealt with the diversity of the Faerie Glenn Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Webb, 2022), where 103 species from 31 families were recorded. When comparing the two surveys, it was found that 42 species from 21 families were recorded from both reserves.

Family diversity: Of the 35 spider families collected from GNR (Tables 1 & 2), the most species-rich families were the Salticidae (20 spp.), Gnaphosidae (12 spp.), followed by the Lycosidae (11 spp.), while 16 families are represented by singletons.

Endemicity: Eight species (7.1%) sampled at GNR have a wide distribution wider than Africa, while 37.5% are African endemics (AE) and 25.9% are Southern African endemics and 27.8% are South African endemics.

Three species are Gauteng endemics, two Idiopidae species *Galeosoma hirsutum* Hewitt, 1916 and *G. pallidum* Hewitt, 1916 and a Sicariidae species *Loxosceles speluncarum* Simon, 1893. Three species are near endemics: *Calommata transvaalica* Hewitt, 1916 of the Atypidae and *Idiops gunningi* Hewitt, 1913 of the Idiopidae are also recorded from Limpopo and *Loxosceles parramae* Newlands, 1981 (Sicariidae) is also recorded from the Free State.

Species of special concern: The following four species are of special concern.

1. *Calommata transvaalica* —Vulnerable

Figures 5–8. *Calommata transvaalica*. 5–6. Male. 7–8. Female. Photo credits: 5 & 7. Charles Haddad. 6. Ian Engelbrecht. 7. Charles Haddad. 8. M. Benic.

Calommata transvaalica is a South African endemic described in 1916 from Roodeplaat, South Africa. It is known only from the Gauteng and Limpopo provinces (Soutpansberg and Blouberg). Parts of its habitat have been threatened in Gauteng due to crop cultivation and urban development, and the species is suspected to occur at fewer than 10 locations. It is therefore listed as Vulnerable under the B criterion (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020).

2. *Loxosceles speluncarum* —Vulnerable

Figures 9–10. *Loxosceles speluncarum* female. Photo credits: Jarrod Todd.

Loxosceles speluncarum is known only from three cave complexes in the Fountain area in Pretoria. It is a troglobite cave species that are more abundant in totally dark areas where they have been

recorded from crevices or wandering around on the cave walls. This species is potentially threatened by disturbance of its specialist cave habitat, and is therefore listed as Vulnerable under criterion D2 (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021a).

3. *Galeosoma hirsutum* —Endangered

Figures 11–12. *Galeosoma hirsutum*. 11. Female 12. Abdomen. Photo credits: A.S. Dippenaar-Schoeman.

Galeosoma hirsutum is a Gauteng endemic described by Hewitt (1916) from Roodeplaat. This species is known from fewer than five extant locations and is threatened throughout its range by urban development. It therefore qualifies for listing as Endangered under criterion B (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021b).

4. *Galeosoma pallidum* —Endangered

Figures 13–14. *Galeosoma pallidum*. 13. Female. 14. Abdomen. Photo credits: A.S. Dippenaar-Schoeman.

Galeosoma pallidum is a Gauteng endemic described by Hewitt (1916) from Saltpan. The species is recorded from a few localities, with six recorded prior to 1915. Currently extant at fewer than five locations and threatened throughout its range by urban development. This species qualifies for listing as Endangered under criterion B (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021b).

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Figures 15–30. Species from Groenkloof Nature Reserve. 15. *Benoitia ocellata* (Agelenidae). 16. *Neoscona hirta* (Araneidae). 17. *Cyrtophora citricola* (Araneidae). 18. *Cyphalonotus larvatus* (Araneidae). 19. *Caponia spiralifera* (Caponiidae). 20. *Cheiracanthium* sp. (Cheiracanthiidae). 21. *Clubiona bevisi* (Clubionidae). 22. *Trephopoda parvipalpa* (Gnaphosidae). 23. *Hogna transvaalica* (Lycosidae). Oxyopidae: 24. *Oxyopes bothai*. 25. *Oxyopes affinis*. 26. *Oxyopes longispinosus*. 27. *Oxyopes jacksoni*. 28. *Vidole sothoana* (Phyxelididae). 29. *Afropisaura rothiformis* (Pisauridae). 30. *Eleleis limpopo* (Prodidomidae). Photo credits: Peter Webb.

Figures 31–44. Species from Groenkloof Nature Reserve. Salticidae: 31. *Evarcha flagellaris*. 32. *Afraflacilla elegans*. 33. *Heliophanus nanus*. 34. *Thyene thynioides*. 35. *Anyphops barbertonensis* (Selenopidae). 36. *Loxosceles parramae* (Sicariidae). Theridiidae: 37. *Tidarren cuneolatum*. 38. *Steatoda capensis*. Thomisidae: 39. *Diaea viridipes*. 40. *Runcinia flavida*. 41. *Synema imitatrix*. Uloboridae: 42. *Uloborus plumipes*. 43. *Miagrammopes brevicaudus*. Zodariidae: 44. *Systenoplacis vandami*. 45. *Capheris schoemanae*. Photo credits: Peter Webb.

APPENDIX 1: Spiders of Groenkloof Nature Reserve (GNR) listing their endemismity (END), conservation status (CON), and country endemismity (CEND).

FAMILIES	SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
AGELENIDAE	<i>Benoitia ocellata</i> (Pocock, 1900) (Fig. 15)	1	LC	AE
AMAUROBIIDAE	<i>Chresiona invalida</i> (Simon, 1898)	3	LC	SAE
ARANEIDAE	<i>Cyphalonotus larvatus</i> (Simon, 1881) (Fig. 18)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Cyrtophora citricola</i> (Forsskål, 1775) (Fig. 17)	0	LC	C
	<i>Nemoscolus tubicola</i> (Simon, 1887)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Neoscona hirta</i> (C.L. Koch, 1844) (Fig. 16)	1	LC	AE
ATYPIDAE	<i>Calommata transvaalica</i> Hewitt, 1916	4	VU	SAE
BEMMERIDAE	<i>Homostola vulpecula</i> Simon, 1892	3	LC	SAE
CAPONIIDAE	<i>Caponia spiralis</i> Purcell, 1904 (Fig. 19)	3	LC	SAE
CHEIRACANTHIIDAE	<i>Cheiracanthium furculatum</i> Karsch, 1879	1	LC	AE
	<i>Cheiramiona florisbadensis</i> Lotz, 2003 (Fig. 20)	3	LC	SAE
CLUBIONIDAE	<i>Clubiona bevisi</i> Lessert, 1923 (Fig. 21)	2	LC	STHE
CORINNIDAE	<i>Messapus martini</i> Simon, 1898	1	LC	AE
CTENIDAE	<i>Ctenus transvaalensis</i> Benoit, 1981	3	LC	SAE
CYRTAUCHENIIDAE	<i>Ancylotrypa pretoriae</i> (Hewitt, 1913)	3	LC	SAE
DICTYNIDAE	<i>Dictyna</i> sp.		NE	
ERESIDAE	<i>Dresserus colsoni</i> Tucker, 1920	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Stegodyphus dumicola</i> Pocock, 1898	2	LC	STHE
GNAPHOSIDAE	<i>Ammoxenus amphalodes</i> Dippenaar & Meyer, 1980	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Camillina cordifera</i> (Tullgren, 1910)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Drassodes stationis</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Ibala arcus</i> (Tucker, 1923)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Micaria beaufortia</i> (Tucker, 1923)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Setaphis subtilis</i> (Simon, 1897)	0	LC	C
	<i>Trephopoda parvipalpa</i> (Tucker, 1923) (Fig. 22)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Xerophaeus aurariarum</i> Purcell, 1907	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Zelotes corrugatus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Zelotes frenchi</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Zelotes fuliginus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	1	LC	AE
<i>Zelotes scrutatus</i> (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872)	1	LC	AE	
IDIOPIDAE	<i>Ctenolophus fenoulheti</i> Hewitt, 1913	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Galeosoma hirsutum</i> Hewitt, 1916	5	EN	SAE
	<i>Galeosoma pallidum</i> Hewitt, 1915	5	EN	SAE
	<i>Galeosoma planiscutatum</i> Hewitt, 1919	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Idiops gunningi</i> Hewitt, 1913	4	DD	SAE
<i>Segregara transvaalensis</i> (Hewitt, 1913)	3	LC	SAE	
LINYPHIIDAE	<i>Microlinyphia sterilis</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Ostearius melanopygius</i> (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1880)	0	LC	C
LYCOSIDAE	<i>Allocosa exserta</i> Roewer, 1959	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Allocosa gracilitarsis</i> (Purcell, 1903)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Allocosa lawrencei</i> (Roewer, 1951)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Foveosa foveolata</i> (Purcell, 1903)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Hogna spenceri</i> (Pocock, 1898)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Hogna transvaalica</i> (Simon, 1898) (Fig. 23)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Pardosa crassipalpis</i> Purcell, 1903	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Pardosa manubriata</i> Simon, 1898	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Proevippa albiventris</i> (Simon, 1898)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Proevippa fascicularis</i> (Purcell, 1903)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Trabea purcelli</i> Roewer, 1951	1	LC	AE

FAMILIES	SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
OXYOPIDAE	<i>Oxyopes affinis</i> Lessert, 1915 (Fig. 25)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Oxyopes bothai</i> Lessert, 1915 (Fig. 24)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Oxyopes jacksoni</i> Lessert, 1915 (Fig. 27)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Oxyopes longispinosus</i> Lawrence, 1938 (Fig. 26)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Oxyopes morpho</i> sp. 3			NE
	<i>Peucetia transvaalica</i> Simon, 1896	1	LC	AE
PALPIMANIDAE	<i>Palpimanus transvaalicus</i> Simon, 1893	3	LC	SAE
PHILODROMIDAE	<i>Suemus punctatus</i> Lawrence, 1938	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Thanatus vulgaris</i> Simon, 1870	0	LC	C
PHOLCIDAE	<i>Smeringopus natalensis</i> Lawrence, 1947	2	LC	STHE
PHYXELIDIDAE	<i>Vidole sothoana</i> Griswold, 1990 (Fig. 28)	2	LC	STHE
PISAURIDAE	<i>Afropisaura rothiformis</i> (Strand, 1908) (Fig. 29)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Euprosthopsis pulchella</i> (Pocock, 1902)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Rothus aethiopicus</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
PRODIDOMIDAE	<i>Austrodomus scaber</i> (Purcell, 1904)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Eleleis limpopo</i> Rodrigues & Rheims, 2020 (Fig. 30)	1	LC	AE
SALTICIDAE	<i>Afraflacilla elegans</i> (Wesołowska & Cumming, 2008) (Fig. 32)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Evarcha flagellaris</i> Haddad & Wesołowska, 2011	1	LC	AE
	<i>Evarcha prosimilis</i> Wesołowska & Cumming, 2008 (Fig. 31)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Heliophanus debilis</i> Simon, 1901	1	LC	AE
	<i>Heliophanus infaustus</i> (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Heliophanus nanus</i> Wesołowska, 2003 (Fig. 33)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Heliophanus orchestra</i> Simon, 1886	1	LC	AE
	<i>Heliophanus pistaciae</i> Wesołowska, 2003	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Heliophanus pygmaeus</i> Wesołowska & Russell-Smith, 2000	1	LC	AE
	<i>Hyllus brevitarsis</i> Simon, 1902	1	LC	AE
	<i>Natta horizontalis</i> Karsch, 1879	1	LC	AE
	<i>Nigorella hirsuta</i> Wesołowska, 2009	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Nigorella hirsuta</i> Wesołowska, 2009	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Pellenes bulawayoensis</i> Wesołowska, 2000	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Phlegra certa</i> Wesołowska & Haddad, 2009	1	LC	AE
	<i>Phlegra karoo</i> Wesołowska, 2006	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Phlegra pusilla</i> Wesołowska & van Harten, 1994	1	LC	AE
	<i>Pseudicius gracilis</i> Haddad & Wesołowska, 2011	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Thyene natalii</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thyene thyenioides</i> (Lessert, 1925) (Fig. 34)	1	LC	AE
<i>Tusitala barbata</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1902	1	LC	AE	
SCYTODIDAE	<i>Scytodes caffra</i> Purcell, 1904	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Scytodes flagellata</i> Purcell, 1904	3	LC	SAE
SELENOPIDAE	<i>Anyphops barbertonensis</i> (Lawrence, 1940) (Fig. 35)	1	LC	AE
SICARIIDAE	<i>Loxosceles parramae</i> Newlands, 1981 (Fig. 36)	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Loxosceles speluncarum</i> Simon, 1893	5	VU D2	SAE
SPARASSIDAE	<i>Palystes superciliosus</i> L. Koch, 1875	2	LC	STHE
STASIMOPIDAE	<i>Stasimopus oculus</i> Pocock, 1897	3	LC	SAE
THERAPHOSIIDAE	<i>Brachionopus pretoriae</i> Purcell, 1904	3	DD	SAE
	<i>Harpactira hamiltoni</i> Pocock, 1902	3	LC	SAE
THERIDIIDAE	<i>Latrodectus geometricus</i> C.L. Koch, 1841	0	LC	C
	<i>Steatoda capensis</i> Hann, 1990 (Fig. 38)	0	LC	C
	<i>Theridion purcelli</i> O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Tidarren cuneolatum</i> (Tullgren, 1910) (Fig. 37)	1	LC	AE

FAMILIES	SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
THOMISIDAE	<i>Diaea puncta</i> Karsch, 1884	1	LC	AE
	<i>Diaea viridipes</i> Strand, 1909 (Fig. 39)	3	DD	SAE
	<i>Monaeses austrinus</i> Simon, 1910	1	LC	AE
	<i>Runcinia aethiops</i> (Simon, 1901)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Runcinia flavida</i> (Simon, 1881) (Fig. 40)	0	LC	C
	<i>Synema imitatrix</i> (Pavesi, 1883) (Fig. 41)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Tmarus comellinii</i> Garcia-Neto, 1989	1	LC	AE
	<i>Xysticus fagei</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE
	<i>Afrocto martini</i> (Simon, 1897)	2	LC	STHE
ULOBORIDAE	<i>Miagrammopes brevicaudus</i> O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1882 (Fig. 43)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Uloborus plumipes</i> Lucas, 1846 (Fig. 42)	0	LC	C
ZODARIIDAE	<i>Cydrela schoemanae</i> Jocqué, 1991	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Diores poweri</i> Tucker, 1920	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Mastidiores</i> sp.		NE	
	<i>Systemoplacis vandami</i> (Hewitt, 1916)	3	LC	SAE